

LINGUISTIC STUDY ON THE TERMINOLOGY OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7922301>

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Annotatsion.

This article is devoted to a linguistic study of terms related to information technology. This article shows the process of integration of terms and progressive development of the field of terminology. In addition, the given article presents the processes of dividing IT terms into groups and the methods of morphological aspect of creating computer terms.

Key words.

lexicon, terminology, linguistic research, "information revolution", globalization, "terminological explosions", computerization.

Nowadays, various devices based on computers and information technologies are used in all aspects of our society, so the terminology is moving from the lexicon of experts to the category of general vocabulary, and the frequency of their use is also expanding. It is known that there are different approaches to the definition of terms in linguistic research, so this issue does not lose its relevance. In many definitions given to the term, its features such as expressing special subjects and concepts, being limited to the performance of a special task, providing information about a scientific concept, signifying concepts related to a special field, not having expressiveness and emotionality are noted.

The end of the twentieth century is characterized by rapid scientific and technological progress that led to the "information revolution". The rapid development of science and technology always leads to a sharp increase in the number of new terms in new fields of knowledge, which are called "terminological explosions". The field of information and communication technologies is one of the most advanced fields in terms of innovation. Most of the inventions in this field

appear in the United States, so they get their designation from the English language. However, the global nature of computerization has led to the internationalization of computer vocabulary.

Many computers are used not only in professional life, but also in everyday life. As a result, many computer terms have moved from the realm of special language to common colloquial language. As a result, computer jargon is formed.

Mastering computer vocabulary occurs simultaneously with the use of information communication innovations. This leads to the simultaneous integration of reality and candidacy. Words that had a terminological meaning a few years ago are now so widely used that it leads to their revision and loss of their "special" meaning. This happens with the rapid development of certain fields of science or technology, as in the field of computer technology, a gradual transition of individual terms from professional to everyday use begins.

In modern linguistics, "analogs" and homonyms of technical products (tablets, mobile phones) based on software platforms of the same name are used in many fields. In addition, other similar examples can be given: blue screen - blue background, the term blue window is a clear proof of this. Today, the term "blue screen" is gradually entering the common vocabulary in standard instructions and software manuals as a term understandable to Russian and Uzbek-speaking computer users. Also, a new lexical-semantic variant of this term was formed in English - user (everyone who works with a computer) - user. As we can see, the above examples are a parallel process of determining the vocabulary, that is, terminology in the field of computer technology, and this process has a significant positive trend in the national language environment. This process contributes to the progressive development of the field of terminology.

The relevance of research in the field of terminology related to modern information technologies comes from the fact that computer terminology is not static. On the contrary, it is always in dynamic development, developing and enriching itself with new terms. Despite many scientific works devoted to the computer dictionary and its translation, there is no complete information about the structural differentiation of terms, word formation methods and term systems.

Various factors affecting the development of the computer terminological system, including information on extralinguistic factors, the computerization of English-speaking societies and the entire world community, the creation and distribution of the Internet, lead to the globalization processes of this field, the expansion of the English language, and the priority of linguistic coding of concepts.

The word computer consists of systematic terms, which can be divided into the following groups:

1. Terms associated with common words. Such terms are formed when frequently used words have meanings specific to IT (information technologies). In this case, the term expresses the meaning of a general word (for example. card - karta, chat - suhbat, break - tanaffus, driver - haydovchi, standard - standart, key - tugma, copy - nusxalash, delete - o'chirish, page - sahifa, programme - dastur, cookie - kuki fayllari, error - xato).

2. General terms operating not only in the system of terms related to computer technology, but also in other fields of science and technology (for example, in the context of a computer, the term driver denotes a program that controls the input and output of information).

3. The special terms related only to the computer are the following. For example, cyber-security, cybernetics, hardware, cyberprofiles, technomedia, electronic cabinet, electronic money, hyperlink, hypertext, cyberspace, microblog, cybercomputer (cybercreek, cybernetics, hardware, cyberprofile, technomedia, e-mail, e-cash, hyperlink, hypertext, cyberlife, microblog, cybercommuter). In such cases, the meaning of the word and the meaning of the term correspond to each other, because the word serves to express only one special concept, that is, the semantics of the term and the word are adequate to the meaning of the term.

4. Terms that have two or more meanings in the computer industry. For example, the term "server" (server) is the name of a computer as a device for accessing the Internet, as well as a program that provides access to the Internet; The term "demonstration" as a verb means to show, and as a noun it means a screen or a monitor; "file" refers to a document, an individual unit of data, and a default menu of applications responsible for file operations.

Its creation also plays a big role in the wider spread of computer terms. The types of word formation are: morphological (affixation suffix, prefix and suffixation), abbreviations, etc.), syntactic (formation of terminological compounds) and morphological-syntactic.

The formation of a new lexical unit by adding an affix (suffix, prefix, interfix, infix, etc.) to the word root is called fixation. The most common ways to associate computer terms are:

1. Prefixation is a method of forming a lexical unit, characterized by the addition of a suffix before the root, that is, a prefix, the most common examples are "kiber-", "e-", "hyper-", "dir", "micro-", "mini-", "multi", "sub-", "super-", "techno-" (for example, cyberaddict, deactivate, e-banking, hyperlink, interface, macroassembler,

microblog, minicomputer, multiaccess, overload, redirect, subdirectory, superclass, technofear, etc.).

2. Suffixing is a method of creating a new lexical unit, which is represented by the addition of a suffix, the most common suffixes of which are "-er", "ware", located between the stem and the end of the word. , "-ise", "-ing", "-(a)tion", "-ish", "-ese", eg scanner, webapp, processor, hack, smiley, boofer, kerning, app, cursor , mail program, authorization, minimization, etc.

3. Prefix-suffix, a method of forming a lexical unit characterized by the addition of both a prefix and a suffix, such as reassignment, disintermediation, co-registration, appearance, refactoring, encoding, supersampling , destructor, deauthorization, unblocking, cyber-hacking, multinet, etc.

It can be seen that the study and generation of computer terms is a complex process consisting of several stages, each of which focuses on the study of a specific aspect of computer terminology, combined with the comprehensive application of general scientific and linguistic methods. requires careful analysis.

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